

NINE WAYS TO WAKE UP: BEDSIDE ALARM CLOCKS DESIGNED BY A 'MEANINGFUL INTERACTION' LEARNING APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

During interaction, people perceive and process varied sensorial information emanating from a product, leading to qualitatively varied experiences on aesthetic, meaning and emotional levels. Navigating a way through the complexity of issues involved in 'design for interaction' (Dfi) is however not easy. This paper presents the foundations and findings of an educational approach to designing for (or by) 'meaningful interaction', which we define as user-product interaction conceived through everyday adjectives and phrases. Product semantics and interaction semantics are compared and contrasted. A product design project (bedside alarm clock) is used as a vehicle for exploring meaning-based Dfi teaching and learning. Students responded well to the educational approach, delivering nine diverse, detailed, and convincing proposals for product interaction. The paper concludes on the 'role' of adjectives in Dfi and the need to synchronize product and interaction semantics to avoid experiential incongruities.

KEYWORDS: *design for interaction, generative design method, meaningful interaction, aesthetics of interaction, semantics*

INTRODUCTION

Industrial designers are not concerned with the specification and configuration of products in isolation, but with reference to people's relations and interactions with those products and for the wider events and experiences that result through product ownership and use (Moggridge, 2007; Suri, 2003; Stott, 2002; Forlizzi & Ford, 2000; Green & Jordan, 1999). User experience, as a combination of cognition, affect, behaviour and instinct (Crilly et al., 2008b; Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008), is a subject that is intrinsic to designing for interaction. It is therefore not surprising that designing for user (or product) experiences has become a subject of considerable attention in design practice and design education in recent years.

In the context of physical artefacts, user-product interactions are fundamental to shaping people's experiences. The conceptualization of interactions at the front end of a project is a critical design step. However, 'design for interaction' (Dfi) is a multifaceted and complex activity, requiring understanding of various characteristics of products, users and usage. Its basic premise is to design a product such that it leaves a trail of positive impressions on people through a series of definable interaction 'events'.

Carefully thought-through interactions are seen as a powerful tool towards adding value to a product and positively influencing people's experiences of that product (Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008). Let us take for example two competing smart phones: one Apple, one Samsung. As with many A-B product comparisons in the current era of high-quality consumer goods, the functionality of both the Apple and Samsung products are similar, their retail prices are comparable, their brands are arguably equally prestigious, their country of manufacture for the most part are likely to be the same, and both products are readily available in stores. Most of these factors are long established as central to people's evaluation of product quality and influential on purchasing decisions (Berkowitz, 1987; Dawar & Parker, 1994). However, faced with a situation of little variance amongst these factors, people must look to other factors – such as product styling, brand image and user-product interaction – to discern which product they prefer amongst many. This paper takes forward ideas for shaping the third of these factors.

Many different approaches may be taken to define the interaction experience offered by a product. These range from sensory-functional analyses (e.g. Locher et al., 2010) to affective analyses such as Kansei Engineering (Schütte et al., 2008;

Nagamachi, 1995). In this present paper, we focus specifically on an approach that may be termed ‘meaningful interaction’, which seeks to make use of meaning concepts (usually expressed as adjectives or phrases) to steer intended interaction experiences in a characterful direction. ‘Meaningful interaction’ is seen as an especially useful approach to Dfl because it can be used to shape the qualitative experience of user-product interaction in a direct and comprehensible manner, by making reference to everyday lexicon and language.

FROM EXPERIENCE OF FORM TO EXPERIENCE OF INTERACTION

The principle that designers add value to products by carefully crafting ‘meanings’ into those products and their related ecology is well known and well studied. Product meanings may be present at a macro-scale, for example simply the presence or absence of a product in a particular environment or at a particular occasion can be the source of meaning. The provenance of a product can also be a deep source of meaning. Closer to the micro-scale, the choice and arrangement of product forms are complex provocateurs of meaning (Krippendorff & Butter, 1984).

Vihma (1995) stressed that whilst product form is inevitably a physical phenomenon, it is crucially an integral part of the perception process between people and products. Norman (1986) adapted visual communication models to the realm of everyday physical products and championed the terms ‘conceptual model’ (of the designer), ‘mental model’ (of the user) and ‘system image’ (of the product), as the three participants involved in ‘expressing’ and ‘discerning’ product functionality. Accordingly, we may say that product form can be ‘read’ to identify visual cues about both the functioning of a product (how we ‘use it’ – e.g. affordances, constraints, mappings, conventions etc.) and its standalone expressive characteristics (what kind of ‘personality’ it possesses – e.g. workmanlike, flamboyant, reliable, premium etc.). It is well known that visual qualities are an important factor in users’ initial evaluations of a product (Hsiao & Chen, 2006; Creusen & Schoormans, 2005; Bloch, 1995). Nelson (1970) alluded to this in his definition of ‘search attributes’ of a product, which may also be described as “... any informational stimuli that can be ascertained through the senses prior to consumption and, according to the consumer, have predictive validity for the product’s quality performance upon consumption” (Steenkamp & Trijp, 1996; p.97). These matters combine into the specialist field of design referred to as ‘product semantics’, concerned with conveying what a product ‘is’, ‘does’ and ‘means’ through product form (Demirbilek & Sener, 2003).

Product semantics represent a visual and static perspective on the role of a product to conjure meaningful experiences and to convey intended messages. This is a statement of fact rather than an accusation, since vision is the dominant sense during product appraisals (Lee et al., 2002). But what happens if we look beyond the visual and the static, towards the multimodal and the dynamic? The answer is that we come across

the concept of ‘meaningful interaction’, where multiple senses might be activated during people’s to-ing and fro-ing between a product during operation. In this process, experience of form gives way to experience of instrumental¹ user-product interaction. Let us explain a little more about how we define meaningful interaction, via the relatively newly coined phrase ‘aesthetics of interaction’ (Hummels & Overbeeke, 2010; Locher et al., 2010).

Aesthetics of Interaction

The definition of ‘aesthetic’ (*adj.*) provided by The Cambridge Dictionaries Online (2011) is “relating to the enjoyment or study of beauty” and as a term has traditionally been associated in industrial design with product appearance or styling (Hollins & Pugh, 1990). This, in turn, has linked aesthetics to the professional design subjects of form, surfaces, materials and finishes influencing product visual properties. But in its contemporary setting, the term ‘aesthetics’ is used to cover multiple senses. For example, the *purring sound of a dishwasher* or the *squashable grip of a toothbrush* are as much aesthetic experiences as the *shimmering finish on a digital camera* or the *sleek lines of a motorcar*. During interaction with a product, we may gain pleasure or displeasure from whichever of our six senses (visual, tactile, kinesthetic, auditory, olfactory, gustatory) are activated at any given time. Designers who seek to define such aesthetic experiences are said to be concerned with *how* an interaction is experienced, or with the *aesthetics of interaction*. They may be concerned with, for example, the *smoothness* of a gear change on a sports car, the *sharpness* of kitchen knife as it effortlessly slices through a fruit, the *comforting softness* of a lounge sofa, or the *slickness of navigation* around a touchscreen operating system. ‘Aesthetics of interaction’ plays to our hedonic needs (Hassenzahl, 2003), since in its absence, a product may still provide acceptable functionality albeit with less panache.

Meaningful Interaction

Meaningful interaction is a concept that combines the principles of both aesthetics of interaction and product communication theory into an actionable approach to Dfl. It seeks to merge the following into a coherent interaction vision.

- Product communication theory: proposing designs for which people will be persuaded to interact with a product in a particular way to achieve a certain task, and be blocked from interactions that are considered detrimental (Crilly et al., 2008a; Greenberg, 2008). Krippendorff (2006) provides the invaluable insight that: “... one always acts according to the meaning of whatever one faces...”.
- Aesthetics of interaction: proposing designs for which the quality of the realized product interaction is appreciated, found pleasurable, irresistible, etc.

1 An instrumental interaction is one where a person is using/operating (or trying to operate) the product. A non-instrumental interaction is performed casually or with intent to explore or fact-find rather than operate – see Demir (2008).

In Desmet & Hekkert's affective framework of product experience (2007), a triad of interrelated sub-experiences (comprising aesthetics, meanings and emotions) is used as an additive approach to defining overall experiences from user-product interactions. What we mean by this is that a progression through the sub-experiences is defined, principally in an iterative manner, involving ever increasing distance away from phenomena of products (e.g. sensorial information emanating from a product, aesthetic experience) towards phenomena of people (e.g. core affect, emotive experience). With this perspective, 'meaningful interaction' essentially becomes the semantics of user-product interaction, or interaction semantics – where the subject of study is the meaning people attach to sensorial information experienced during interaction. In other words, we can say that sensorial information (from an interaction) 'speaks to us' (semiotics, signs) and that we can 'tell something' from it (semantics, meanings).

METHODOLOGY

As alluded to earlier, designers are familiar with using adjectives or phrases to guide form creation in a particular direction, with a view to conveying intended messages through product form and expressive visual characteristics. The central 'problem' in the work reported through this paper was to take the same thinking behind adjectival design approaches to form creation and apply it to meaningful interaction experiences that we may have with new products. That is, how to develop and apply an educational approach that focused not on, for example, generating an adventurous [looking] product but instead generating an adventurous interaction experience with a product? What kind of teaching and learning steps might be required? To do this, a seven-week research and design project was initiated as part of the elective course 'Design for Interaction' given to graduate industrial design students enrolled at the Department of Industrial Design, Middle East Technical University.

Design for Interaction – A Teaching & Learning Framework

The purpose of the 'Design for Interaction' course is to provide students with an introduction to interaction design (IxD) and user experience design (UXD) within the specific context of materialized products. It therefore serves as a bridge between students' skills gained through undergraduate industrial design training and more advanced studies in the fields of product experience. Although the course is necessarily quite broad in its subject matter, a key principle is always that students must apply what they have learned through a relatively long (up to half a semester) major project. Our teaching and learning is tied to a framework of five elements that have been refined over a six-year period. We have found that these elements adequately equip students for macro-level and micro-level ideation and development of interaction experiences for new products.

1. Domains of interaction: The various arrangements in which products can be connected to people.
2. Design communication theory: How people understand the usage of products from the information that products convey.
3. Contexts: Factors outside the control of the designer, which influence and condition the actors and situation in which an interaction takes place and within which design creativity can manifest.
4. User experiences: The various levels at which people can be affected by user-product interactions.
5. Technologies: New and emerging technologies that improve the interactivity of products or offer novel ways for interaction and connectivity to other products.

Design Project - Bedside Alarm Clock

Students used their course learnings to work on meaningful interactions for new bedside alarm clock concepts. This product was chosen because of its good potential for multimodal interaction, its relative simplicity in functionality and because its form need not be constrained by conventions. During the project, students defined an interaction vision, and then realized that vision through individual interaction episodes encountered along the path of interaction. To help navigate the possibilities of multimodal interaction, and to act as a source of idea inspiration, we constructed and made available to students a taxonomy of sensorial information (Figure 1) from an associated literature review. The taxonomy was inspired in part by the Kansei approach to product evaluation (Satterfield, 2003), in which a product is regarded as a transmitter of sensorial information across sensory modalities.

The project was managed through six stages, which in combination defined a method for ideation of meaningful interactions. Each stage is now described in detail.

Stage 1 – 'Visualized Connotations'. Each student was assigned an adjective, which would later form the basis of a product interaction proposal (adaptive, amusing, calm, charming, cheerful, engaging, helpful, innovative, simple). The adjectives were chosen by the course tutors so as to stimulate a wide variety of different interaction approaches and positive user experiences. Adjectives with negative connotations were not used. Krippendorff (2006) insists that without such adjective or associative constructions, it would be difficult for people (in our case, designers) to distinguish the properties of things (yet to be realized). Students made a semantic exploration of their assigned adjective and prepared seven A3 posters, as follows.

- i) By using <www.thesaurus.com> students decided on the particular 'sense' in which they would explore their adjective, and noted down given synonyms for that sense (Figure 2.a).
- ii) By using <www.dictionary.com> students chose a definition of their adjective and two preferred synonyms, which when

Figure 1. Taxonomy of sensorial information transmittable by physical artefacts.

LIKABLE
LOVABLE
 EYE-CATCHING
 DESIRABLE FASCINATING
CHARMING
 APPEALING PLEASANT
ELEGANT
 PLEASING
 CUTE

a

DEFINITIONS

CHARMING: pleasing;
 delightful: a charming
 child.

ELEGANT: graceful in form
 or movement: an elegant
 wave of the hand.

FASCINATING: of great
 interest or attraction;
 enchanting; charming;
 captivating: a fascinating
 story; fascinating jewelry.

b

c

d

e

f

**SENSORIAL INFO TO
 CONNOTATION**

- ATTRACTING INTEREST
- DISTINGUISHES THE PRODUCT
- INVITE USER TO TOUCH/FEEL
- FEELS EXTRAORDINARY
- BEAUTY IN DETAILS
- A SIMPLE 'WOW' MOMENT

g

Figure 2.a-g. Example of student poster series for Stage 1 'Visualized Connotations' - for the assigned adjective 'charming' - (by Ahmet Burak Aktaş).

combined would verbally communicate the essence of the connotations that the student sought to evoke (Figure 2.b).

- iii) Students collated high-quality images of products (Figure 2.c-d) and non-products (Figure 2.e-f) that they considered to strongly embody their adjective and synonyms.
- iv) From their ‘product’ images, students identified and justified which kinds of sensorial information they considered to convey their adjective and synonyms (Figure 2.g).

Stage 2 – ‘Design Brief’. Students were made aware that the semantic explorations of the preceding stage would be taken forward in the context of meaningful interaction. The full design brief was distributed, explaining that the assigned adjectives would form the basis of product and interaction ideation and development. Students were free to determine the target user for their product, based on an understanding of who may value an ‘...adjective...’ interaction.

Stage 3 – ‘Acting-Out Interactions’. This stage asked students to think deeply about their adjectives and synonyms and to work towards an interaction vision by building relevant usage scenarios and considering how an ‘...adjective...’ interaction might be experienced. Students physically acted-out their interaction and storyline ideas using supplied primitive forms (Figure 3).

Stage 4 – ‘Product Critique’. As an in-class exercise, students were divided into groups to source Internet images and videos for ‘bedside alarm clocks’. Each group created a map of product attributes that they found worthwhile for discussion, including features, interaction, forms, and technology.

Stage 5 – ‘Product Development and 1-to-1 Critiques’. Students continued to develop their ideas by creating a storyboard (visual narrative) of potential interactions and product attributes. At this point, they were reminded to consider how each of the five course elements would influence their designs, but to work holistically on the product.

Stage 6 – ‘Final Presentation’. The completed projects were submitted as (i) a presentation board (Figure 4.a), (ii) a fact sheet, (iii) a lo-fi physical mock-up for live acting-out of interactions, (iv) augmented reality content that projected multi-modal information onto presentation boards and mock-ups, bringing static visuals/objects ‘to life’ (Figure 4.b).

Figure 4.a-b. ‘Poly’ bedside alarm clock with CHARMING interaction: example presentation board and augmented reality mock-up (by Ahmet Burak Aktaş).

Figure 3. Acting-out possible interaction and storyline ideas using supplied primitive forms (by Ahmet Burak Aktaş).

ANALYSIS OF MEANINGFUL INTERACTION PROPOSALS

Figure 5 illustrates the nine bedside alarm clock proposals, which are now described in detail.

‘Adaptive Interaction’ in the sense of serving or able to adapt; showing or contributing to adaptation. Chosen synonyms: ‘flexible’ (elastic, stretchy, malleable) and ‘adjustable’ (modifiable, tailor-made, made to fit). ‘Mr.Quiet’ is a mechanical product ‘creature’ adaptive to users’ sleep location and posture. Each day the user must set the alarm based on the amount of sleep he or she wants to have, by pulling and extending the creature’s tongue. Printed on the tongue is a scale of hours/minutes and a comment on whether the sleep duration is sufficient or not. The product is clipped to a nearby object (e.g. pillow, pyjama) and quietly makes its way back to the clip as the hours of sleep pass. It operates discretely by sounding its alarm and vibration in close proximity to the person sleeping.

‘Amusing Interaction’ in the sense of pleasantly entertaining or diverting. Chosen synonyms: ‘gratifying’ (tending to gratify; giving or causing satisfaction; pleasing) and ‘witty’ (possessing wit in speech or writing; amusingly clever in perception and expression: a witty writer). The operation of ‘Monolight’ uses magnetic resistance embedded in various locations around the anonymous looking cuboid body. The user sets the alarm time with a special magnetic stylus: as the magnetic resistance is felt more strongly, so the speed of the alarm adjustment increases. This gives a precision kinesthetic feel to the interaction, as well as a sense of amusement through its novelty. The amusement continues at alarm time, when a purring cat is sounded, gradually morphing into a wild cat if the alarm is not cancelled. To cancel the alarm, ‘Monolight’ must be turned on its head and into a recess, which requires effort to act against magnetic repulsion – surely waking up the user in the process.

‘Calm Interaction’ in the sense of peaceful, quiet. Chosen synonyms: ‘harmonious’ (forming a pleasingly consistent whole, congruous) and ‘smooth’ (free from projections or unevenness of surface; not rough). ‘Zen’ harnesses elements of nature for its interaction, and through each element a sense of calm is conveyed. The product gradually illuminates (mimicking sunrise) and emits initially quiet but increasingly loud sounds as the alarm time approaches, to get the body prepared peacefully for waking up. Users define a soundscape by layering different ‘nature’ sounds (e.g. leaves, campfire, thunder) to wake up to. Each sound is represented tangibly as a pebble, making the placing and replacing of pebbles a ritualistic approach to alarm setting and cancelling.

‘Charming Interaction’ in the sense of pleasing; delightful: a charming child. Chosen synonyms: ‘elegant’ (graceful in form or movement: an elegant wave of the hand) and ‘fascinating’ (of great interest or attraction; enchanting; charming; captivating: a fascinating story). The icosahedron product form of ‘Poly’ is purposefully captivating to generate curiosity and desire to pick it up and handle it. The product takes on the responsibility not only to tell the user when to wake up but

also when to go to bed (if desired) in an elegant, carefully composed manner. It has unobtrusive and clear functions shared with a smart phone (app) interface. In the morning, a random face of the icosahedron lights up, asking the user to pay special attention to locating it and shutting off the alarm by placing the illuminated face downward.

‘Cheerful Interaction’ in the sense of promoting or inducing cheer, pleasantness, brightness. Chosen synonyms: ‘joyful’ (causing or bringing joy, as an event, a sight, or news; delightful) and ‘happy’ (delighted, pleased, or glad, as over a particular thing). ‘Daisy’ is animated, colorful and playful. It brings brightness at the time of waking up. The head of the clock – containing a light and ringer – leans over as it counts down to the alarm time, getting ever closer to the sleeping person’s head and readying them for waking up. Unusually, one interacts directly with the ‘clock hands’ to set the alarm time; once the alarm time is reached, the mechanical hands literally ‘clap’ to sound the alarm.

‘Engaging Interaction’ in the sense of winning; attractive; pleasing. Chosen synonyms: ‘attractive’ (arousing interest or engaging one’s thought, consideration) and ‘inviting’ (attractive, alluring, or tempting). ‘DingDong’ tries to make the waking up process more engaging through a multi-sensory experience. Two minutes ahead of the alarm time, the product starts to warn the user with increasing auditory and visual alerts. When it is time to wake up, the display physically pops out and exposes the loudspeaker, resulting in an unsilenced and louder alarm tone. The display also exhibits a swinging motion to alert the user. Making an effort to place the display back on its base cancels the alarm.

‘Helpful Interaction’ in the sense of giving or rendering aid or assistance like a caring, human-oriented and humanlike friend. Chosen synonyms: ‘friendly’ (characteristic of or befitting a friend; showing friendship) and ‘humane’ (tenderness, compassion, and sympathy for people and animals, especially for the suffering or distressed). ‘IntelliWake’ is helpful in that it provides humanlike advice and greetings on its display, along with feedback about sufficiency of sleep durations based on the planned alarm time. Throughout the sleeping hours, the product displays how much sleep time is left. With the accompanying app, users can track their sleep durations over time and use the information to change sleeping habits for the better.

‘Innovative Interaction’ in the sense of using or showing new methods, ideas; tending to introduce something new for the first time. Chosen synonyms: ‘creative’ (characterized by originality of thought; having or showing imagination) and ‘new’ (fresh and unused, up-to-date, novel). Innovative interaction is provided in ‘GameClock’ through gamification of the waking up process and the form and functions provided on the product. The product is used as part of a social network, offering ‘points’ to members based on whether they can wake up early compared to their friends. Points are deducted for snoozing and delaying the getting-up process. Points turn to real rewards once a total has been reached, depending on the interests of the social network.

‘Simple Interaction’ in the sense of clear, easy to understand, deal with, use, etc. Chosen synonyms: ‘quiet’ (not showy or obtrusive, subdued) and ‘self-explanatory’ (explaining itself, needing no explanation, obvious). In ‘Sooth Up’, dual functionality of a bedside lamp and alarm clock is provided. The product body is used as a tangible joystick controller offering simple movements: the x-axis mapped to alarm time up/down, and the y-axis mapped to lamp intensity up/down. To simulate the dawn, the product gently glows and its alarm becomes audibly louder as the alarm time approaches. Snoozing or cancelling is mapped to pushing the product body forwards or backwards.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

The portfolio of product designs demonstrated very successfully to students how changes in the qualities of multimodal interaction dramatically affect user experiences. Furthermore, the variety in visual attributes of the proposals illustrates how changes in interaction vision can help steer product designs away from convention to potentially fruitful commercial ground. Students commented that the ‘element-based’ approach to learning interaction theory and terminology prepared them well for the design project. We would like to share our main observations regarding the process and possible improvements to designing for meaningful interaction.

In retrospect, it seems necessary to clarify the role of the adjective. All adjectives were used as a common tool to help

achieve positive user experiences from interesting new products. The design task was to ‘use’ the adjective (generatively, by designers) and not to explicitly ‘convey’ the adjective (evaluatively, to users). Seen this way, we did not expect product proposals to unequivocally communicate the adjective. It would be acceptable for users to detect the essence of the adjective or its synonyms, with the more important effect of being left with a positive product impression from the interaction. In this regard, the educational approach we took is best described as ‘design by’ rather than ‘design for’ meaningful interaction, in the sense that the adjectives were principally used as a design tool for students to be inspired and guided in their ideation.

The location of the interaction experience was another issue raised during the work. In the portfolio of designs, we see that where adjectival emphasis is placed can change. For example, a variation in meaningful interaction occurred during product set-up, operation, set-down, and storage/standby. We saw adjectives (i) driving overall product/interaction appraisals (e.g. the product *is cheerful*), (ii) shaping overall user affect/experience (e.g. the product *makes me cheerful*), (iii) shaping affect/experience when being woken (e.g. the product *wakes me up cheerfully*), and (iv) influencing product/interaction appraisals when the alarm sounds (e.g. the product *is cheerful when when the alarm goes off*). It is worth noting that a bedside alarm clock is a ‘set and wait’ type of product with long periods of inactivity, in contrast to an ‘interactive’ product such as a food mixer, hairdryer or smart phone – where meaningful interaction may manifest more obviously and frequently.

Figure 5. [From left to right, top to bottom] Completed bedside alarm clocks with ‘adaptive’, ‘amusing’, ‘calm’, ‘charming’, ‘cheerful’, ‘engaging’, ‘helpful’, ‘innovative’, and ‘simple’ interaction.

Regarding crossovers between product semantics and interaction semantics, students were specifically asked to design for interaction, but of course not without a degree of attention to product form and styling. Inevitably the choice and design of product elements for user-product interaction affects the overall form and stylistic direction of product proposals (and vice versa). For future work, we conclude that it would be worth considering how to integrate 'product semantics' and 'interaction semantics' into a unified method. This would require special attention to experiential incongruities that may arise from misaligned styling and interaction visions.

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